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Solubility and aggregation behavior of dendronized poly(*p*-benzamide)s¹

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A series of Fréchet dendronized poly(*p*-benzamide)s have been synthesized. To attach the dendron-functionalities to the poly(*p*-benzamide) backbone, a propargyl side chain was introduced to *p*-aminobenzoic acid. Then, copper catalyzed azide-alkyne cycloaddition was used to click a first generation (G₁) respectively a second generation (G₂) Fréchet-dendron azide onto the amino acid monomer. The resulting amino acids were polymerized using triphenylphosphite to obtain a poorly organo-soluble G₁-dendronized polymer and a non-aggregating G₂-dendronized polymer showing good organo-solubility. Furthermore, a strictly alternating non-aggregating G₁-TEG-dendronized polymer with good organo-solubility was synthesized. The aggregation behavior of these polymers was investigated by dynamic light scattering.

¹ Supporting information for this article is available at the bottom of the article's abstract page, which can be accessed from the journal's homepage at <http://www.macros.wiley-vch.de>, or from the author.

Introduction

There has been a great interest in molecular rods that can be assembled in precise constitution from individual building blocks.^[1] While there are many reports of stannanes^[1b,1c,1e] and poly(phenylene ethynylene)s,^[1a,1b,1d,1e] which require carbon-carbon bond formation for their synthesis, there are only a few examples of aromatic amide rods present.^[1g,1h] Such peptide derivatives can be built up via peptide bond formation by use of the well-developed peptide chemistry. Poly(*p*-benzamide)s are suitable for this approach due to their inherently extended chain structure.^[2] Yet there are some challenges in working with these materials. Because of the distinct formation of hydrogen-bonds and π - π -stacking^[3] between the chains in aromatic polyamides, these polymers are only soluble in hydrogen-breaking solvents like dimethylacetamide/lithium chloride mixtures or concentrated sulfuric acid.^[4]

To improve the solubility and study the aggregation behavior of poly(*p*-benzamide)s in solution, block copolymers^[5] have been built or *N*-protective groups^[6] introduced. Another approach is to introduce flexible alkyloxy side chains. We recently described the synthesis of a triethylene glycol-grafted (TEG) poly(*p*-benzamide) which showed good solubility in most common organic solvents but still formed aggregates in solution.^[7] This approach, however, results in a planarization of the neighboring phenyl rings in the poly(*p*-benzamide)s, thus leading to increased aggregation of the flat polymers via π -interactions. A further method to reduce aggregation is the use of dendritic side groups as present in dendronized polymers, pioneered and extensively studied by the Schlüter group.^[8]

Here, we present a modular synthetic approach to sterically demanding *p*-aminobenzoic acid monomers using Fréchet dendrons^[9] as side groups. Polymerization of these bulky monomers is expected to increase solubility on the one hand and prevent aggregation via π -interactions.

Experimental Part

Materials

Dioxane (Acros) was stored over molecular sieves (3 Å). All other chemicals and solvents were obtained from Acros and used as received. Compounds **1**,^[10] **4a**, **4b**^[9,11] and **9**^[7] were prepared according to reported procedures. Synthesis of the monomers **8a**, **8b** and the dimeric monomer **10** is described in the supporting information.

Instrumental

All ¹H NMR (300 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (75 MHz) spectra were recorded on a Bruker AC (300 MHz) FT NMR spectrometer. ¹H NMR (400 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (100MHz) spectra were recorded on a Bruker AMX (400 MHz) FT NMR spectrometer. ¹⁹F NMR (400 MHz) spectra and ¹³C NMR heating experiments were recorded on a Bruker DRX (400 MHz) FT NMR spectrometer. Chemical shifts (δ) were given in ppm relative to the TMS signal. RP-HPLC analysis was performed on a Hewlett-Packard HP 1090 liquid chromatograph equipped with PerfectSil column (MZ-Analysentechnik GmbH, Mainz, Germany, 250 x 4.0 mm; 120 ODS-25 mm). The samples were eluted with an acetonitrile/water gradient (buffered with 0.1% TFA), starting from 10% acetonitrile and rising to 90% over a period of 35 min and maintained constant for additional 10 min. UV detection was performed at 254 nm. Melting points were recorded on a FP 62 Mettler Toledo. Field desorption mass spectra were measured on a Finnigan MAT 95 and ESI mass spectra on a Micromass Q-TOF Ultima 3. Gel permeation chromatography (GPC) with chloroform was carried out on an instrument consisting of a Waters 717 plus autosampler, a TSP Spectra Series P 100 pump, and a set of three PSS SDV columns (10⁶/10⁵/10⁴ g/mol). Signal detection was performed with TSP Spectra System UV 2000 (UV 254 nm) and a Wyatt Optilab DSP (refractive index). Dynamic light scattering was

performed on a ALV-8GF goniometer with an ALV7000 correlator and a HeNe-Uniphase 22mW Laser with a wavelength of 632.8 nm.

Synthesis of Polymers

Polycondensation of compound **8a**: (**P-G₁**)

A mixture of compound **8a** (200 mg, 0.373 mmol), triphenyl phosphite (0.373 mmol) and pyridine (0.2 mL) in 0.8 mL anhydrous NMP was heated under argon at 100°C. After stirring over night, the reaction mixture was poured in methanol. The resulting precipitate was centrifuged and washed several times with methanol, water and again with methanol. The resulting yellow solid was insoluble in most common organic solvents. It was completely soluble in NMP and hot DMSO at low concentrations.

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, d⁶-DMSO): see supporting information Figure S1.

Polycondensation of compound **8b**: (**P-G₂**)

A mixture of compound **8b** (140 mg, 0.146 mmol), triphenyl phosphite (0.146 mmol) and pyridine (0.08 mL) in 0.40 mL anhydrous NMP was heated under argon at 100°C. After stirring over night, the reaction mixture was poured into methanol. The resulting precipitate was centrifuged and washed several times with methanol, water and again with methanol. The resulting yellow solid **P-G₂-a** was soluble in most common organic solvents like chloroform, DMF, DMSO, NMP. A polymer **P-G₂-b** with higher molecular weight resulted from stirring the reaction mixture for three days at higher concentration (0.2 mL anhydrous NMP) at 100°C.

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, d⁶-DMSO): see supporting information Figure S2/S3.

Polycondensation of compound **10**: (**P-G₁-TEG**)

A mixture of compound **10** (292 mg, 0.357 mmol), triphenyl phosphite (0.357 mmol) and pyridine (0.24 mL) in 0.70 mL anhydrous NMP was heated under argon at 100°C. After

stirring 48 h, the reaction mixture was poured into methanol. The resulting precipitate was centrifuged and washed several times with methanol, water and again with methanol. The resulting yellow solid **P-G₁-TEG-a** was soluble in most common organic solvents like chloroform, DMF, DMSO, NMP. A polymer **P-G₁-TEG-b** with higher molecular weight resulted from stirring for three days at higher concentration (0.35 mL anhydrous NMP) at 100°C.

¹H-NMR (400 MHz, d⁶-DMSO): see supporting information Figure S4/S5.

Results and Discussion

Synthesis

To study the solubility and aggregation behavior of dendronized poly(*p*-benzamide)s, a modular new route based on the *ortho*-alkylation of *p*-aminosalicylic acid was developed.^[7] First of all we synthesized a "clickable" reactant **3** enabling us to click several alkyl azides with different functionalities via the copper catalyzed azide-alkyne cycloaddition^[12] to the monomer structure. In our case we decided to attach bulky and sterically hindered Fréchet dendrons of first **4a** and second **4b** generation as the azide derivatives. They were synthesized according to the literature.^[9,11]

The monomers were synthesized based on *p*-aminosalicylic acid as outlined in Scheme 1. The *N*-*tert*-butyloxycarbonyl (Boc) protection was accomplished according to the literature to afford compound **1**.^[10] Based on this compound the "clickable" reactant **3** was synthesized in two steps. Firstly, the corresponding ester and ether **2** was formed in a Williamson ether reaction with propargyl bromide in 92% yield. This was followed by an alkaline ester hydrolysis to yield the "clickable" reactant **3** (82%). To attach the two dendron azides **4a** and **4b** we used the copper catalyzed azide-alkyne cycloaddition yielding the products **5a** (91%) and **5b** (92 %).

<insert Scheme 1 here>

The common copper sulfate/sodium ascorbate system has proved to be a suitable catalyst system in our case.^[12] For deprotection of the *N*-*tert*-butyloxycarbonyl group we used a 1:5 mixture of a trifluoroacetic acid solution in dichloromethane. This procedure afforded the trifluoroacetic acid salts of the corresponding amino acids **6a** and **6b**. Polymerization efforts using these compounds were not successful, caused by premature decarboxylation of the monomers under acidic conditions. The resulting mono-functional monomers dramatically limited the molecular weights of the polymers obtained.

Even during prolonged refrigeration (1-2 weeks) of the trifluoroacetic acid salts a slow decarboxylation could be observed (see supporting information for analysis of the decarboxylation product of **7a**, obtained after Fmoc protection from decarboxylated amino acid **6a**). The presence of decarboxylated monomer disrupts the polycondensation significantly by terminating the growing polymer chains. For this reason we had to gain access to the free amino acids **8a** and **8b**. Our efforts to transfer the trifluoroacetic acid salts of the amino acids directly into the free amino acids after deprotection with TFA were not successful. Our investigations included the use of several weak and strong anion exchange resins (Dowex Marathon WBA, Amberlyst A21, Ambersep 900 OH), distillation with toluene and neutralizing with sodium carbonate respectively sodium hydrogen carbonate. Finally, we developed an indirect route by protection and deprotection of the amino function of the amino acid salts **6a** and **6b**. For the protection we used 9-fluorenylmethylchloroformate (Fmoc-Cl) yielding the Fmoc-protected amino acids **7a** and **7b** (79% and 70%). Subsequent deprotection with 20 vol.-% piperidine in DMF afforded the free amino acids **8a** and **8b** (73% and 67%).

The polycondensation reaction of the monomers **8a** and **8b** was catalyzed by triphenyl phosphite and pyridine in NMP as outlined in Scheme 2.^[13] During the polymerization of the G₁-substituted monomer **8a**, the resulting polymer **P-G₁** already precipitated after several hours.

<insert Scheme 2 here>

P-G₁ was insoluble in most common organic solvents except NMP and hot (100°C) DMSO at low concentrations. Polymerization of the G₂-substituted monomer **8b** yielded a polymer **P-G₂** which was soluble in most common organic solvents (NMP, DMSO, chloroform, THF and others).

In a further study a dimeric monomer **10** with TEG and G₁ side chains was synthesized (Scheme 3) to yield a strictly alternating G₁-TEG-dendronized polymer showing no aggregation and good organo-solubility.

<insert Scheme 3 here>

Solid supported syntheses of oligo(*p*-benzamide)s have previously been reported.^[13] To synthesize the dimeric monomer **10**, monomer **9**^[7] was first attached to a Wang resin. In the next step the deprotection of the Fmoc group was afforded with a 20 vol.-% solution of piperidine in NMP followed by the attachment of the Fmoc protected amino acid **7a** which was previously converted into the corresponding acid chloride using triphosgene. After cleavage from the solid support using a 50 vol.-% solution of TFA in DCM, deprotection of the amino group with a 20 vol.-% solution of piperidine in DMF yielded the dimeric monomer **10** (52%).

The polycondensation of the dimeric monomer **10** was catalyzed by triphenyl phosphite and pyridine in NMP as outlined in Scheme 4. Polymerization of monomer **10** resulted in a polymer which was highly soluble in most common organic solvents. We would like to emphasize that the use of solid supported synthesis is particularly useful for the preparation of oligomers built from different monomer types. In our case, two different types of monomer were used to build a macromonomer which will lead to a strictly alternating copolymer. However, longer heterosequences are conceivable and synthetically feasible, leading to segmented polymers in which a particular monomer sequence is continuously repeated. The interest in sequence control in synthetic polymers has recently received increased interest.^[14] Comparing the overwhelming variety of function and materials properties seen in nature, we believe that sequence control in synthetic polymers will play a key role for future materials developments.

<insert Scheme 4 here>

Characterization of Polymers

Due to its low solubility in chloroform and DMF, gel permeation chromatography (GPC) of the G₁-dendronized polymer could not be performed. Gel permeation chromatography elugrams of the strictly alternating G₁-TEG-dendronized polymer showed bimodal curves (Figure 1). The obtained high molecular weight mode indicated a formation of supramolecular, i.e. non-covalent aggregates. Comparing the intensity of the aggregation peak in GPC elugrams in a polar and a non-polar organic solvent such as chloroform and DMF suggested that the formation and stability of these supramolecular structures are less pronounced in polar solvents (DMF). Gel permeation chromatography of the G₂-dendronized polymers showed a monomodal elugram of similar elution time as observed for the lower molecular weight mode seen

for the G₁-TEG polymer. It did however not show any formation of supramolecular aggregates in DMF or in chloroform (Figure 1).

<insert Figure 1 here>

This is first evidence that the G₂-dendronized polymer rods show no aggregation behavior. However, it should be pointed out that in our case gel permeation chromatography can only be used to discuss aggregation behavior and not to determine the correct molecular weights which were highly underestimated compared to ¹H-NMR end-group analysis (see Table S1 in supporting information). This is due to the fact that preparing an accurate calibration curve for these materials would require defined oligomer and polymer standards of these polymers which were not available. Here, we used polystyrene standards for GPC in DMF and polyethylene glycol standards for GPC in chloroform.

The molecular weights M_n of the G₁- and G₂-dendronized polymers could also be obtained via ¹H-NMR end-group analysis (see supporting information Table S1). The NH₂ end-group at δ = 6.07 ppm was integrated with respect to the amide N-H protons around δ = 10.4 ppm to obtain an estimate for the number average degree of polymerization. The molecular weight M_n of the G₁-TEG-dendronized polymer could not be determined in this manner due to a low-field shift of the NH₂ end-group which led to overlapping with other signals.

Investigations of the aggregation behavior of the G₁-TEG- and G₂-dendronized polymers were accomplished by dynamic light scattering in hexafluoroisopropanol (HFIP) (c = 5 g/L, containing 1mM sodium trifluoroacetate). Measuring the samples after filtration through a 450 nm filter, both polymers showed a small amount (less than 1%; evaluated from the biexponential fit) of higher aggregates with R_h = 25 nm for P-G₁-TEG-b and R_h = 50 nm for P-G₂ (Figure 2). The origin of these aggregates is yet unknown and has to be examined in future

studies. After filtration through a 20 nm filter these aggregates disappeared, yielding non-aggregating polymers ($R_h = 2.0$ nm for P-G₁-TEG-b and $R_h = 2.5$ nm for P-G₂). No formation of aggregates was observed over time (up to 24 h) by DLS after removal of the initially formed aggregates. It is conceivable that the formation of aggregates was due to trace amounts of residual copper ions coordinated to the polymer. In previous studies HFIP solutions of substituted oligo(*p*-benzamide)s showed strong aggregation by DLS and TEM.^[15] Here, DLS did not show the formation of aggregates over time leading us to the conclusion that the Fréchet G₂-dendron is sterically bulky enough to prevent stacking of the oligoamide backbone.

<insert Figure 2 here>

Discussion

The initially prepared Fréchet-G₁-dendron substituted polymer did not exhibit the expected good organo-solubility while the analogous G₂-dendron substituted polymer showed excellent solubility and no aggregation by DLS. Attaching a G₁ side chain to the previously reported organo-soluble but strongly aggregating TEG-dendronized poly(*p*-benzamide),^[7] resulted in a strictly alternating G₁-TEG-dendronized poly(*p*-benzamide), which showed no aggregation by DLS. The G₁-dendron side group is therefore most likely sterically demanding enough to prevent aggregation via π -stacking. However, as the polymer which is exclusively carrying G₁-dendrons shows poor organo solubility, the mobility of the relatively small G₁-dendron is not large enough to support the dissolution process of the rigid rod-like poly(*p*-benzamide) backbone.

In contrast to the G₁-dendronized poly(*p*-benzamide)s, introduction of a second generation dendron (G₂) to the poly(*p*-benzamide) backbone, led to highly soluble polymers caused by its significantly higher mobility. This, in addition to its high steric demand, proved to be an

excellent side group for solubilizing rigid-rod-like polyaramides. The G₂-dendronized poly(*p*-benzamide) gave no indication of aggregation by dynamic light scattering or transmission electron microscopy.

Conclusion

We have reported a new and highly modular synthetic approach to functional *p*-amino-salicylic acid monomers using click chemistry. This approach allowed the introduction of Fréchet dendrons of first (G₁) and second generation (G₂) to the poly(*p*-benzamide) backbone. A third type of polymer, in which first generation Fréchet dendrons and triethylene glycol (TEG) chains alternate has also been prepared.

The strictly alternating G₁-TEG-dendronized polymer shows no aggregation tendency and good organo-solubility. In contrast, the G₁-dendronized homopolymer is poorly organo-soluble whereas the G₂-dendronized homopolymer shows no aggregation tendency and excellent organo-solubility. The aggregation behavior was determined by dynamic light scattering. We therefore conclude that the steric bulk of the G₁-dendron is sufficient enough to prevent π -stacking, yet its solvent interaction is insufficient to support solvation of the rigid-rod-like polyaramide backbone.

These investigations are an important step towards the synthesis of non-aggregating sequence controlled oligomeric and polymeric rods. The modular approach to functional aromatic amino acid monomers will be most useful for the rapid evaluation of monomer libraries carrying substituents of different functionality and steric demand. Using solid supported synthesis, a heterosequence was prepared which upon polymerization yielded a strictly alternating polymer. It is conceivable that this general approach can be extended to larger oligomeric heterosequences which upon polymerization will yield segmented polymers consisting of linear arrays of sequence controlled monomer segments. This approach might help to close the

gap between synthetic homo and copolymers on the one hand and nature's sequence controlled polymers on the other.

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Scheme 1. Synthesis of monomers carrying first (G_1) and second generation (G_2) Fréchet dendrons.

Scheme 2. Polycondensation of the G₁ and G₂ carrying monomers.

Scheme 3. Synthesis of the dimeric monomer carrying a triethylene glycol (TEG) and G₁ side chain.

Scheme 4. Polycondensation of the dimeric monomer.

Figure 1. GPC elugrams of polymers **P-G₂** and **P-G₁-TEG** in DMF (left) and chloroform (right). a/b denote different molecular weight samples (see experimental part).

Figure 2. Dynamic light scattering of the polymers **P-G₂-b** (left) and **P-G₁-TEG-b** (right) at 293K and an scattering angle of $\theta = 30^\circ$ ($c = 5$ g/L in hexafluoroisopropanol containing 1mM sodium trifluoroacetate).

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In this paper the solution and aggregation behavior of dendronized poly(*p*-benzamide)s is studied. Copper catalyzed azid-alkyne cycloaddition was used to attach a first generation (G₁) and a second generation (G₂) Fréchet dendron. Depending on the size of the dendron, a poor organo-soluble (G₁) and a non-aggregating, good organo-soluble (G₂) polymer could be obtained. Furthermore a strictly alternating G₁-TEG-dendronized polymer has been synthesized showing good solubility and no aggregation compared to the parent homopolymer.

graphical abstract:

